

SMART SHOPPING CART IN THE UAE: SURVEY ON THE MARKET NEEDS

Khalid Alzarooni, Khalid Alzarooni, Obaid Salem, Rashid Alhosani, Juma Alali,
Mohamed Abdelrahman, Ahmad Mamdouh Akkad

ABSTRACT

Sanitization became an important concept during the spread of COVID-19 pandemic. COVID-19 has created many challenges for people to face on a daily basis. One of the many challenges people encounter is sanitization of trolley handles when grocery shopping. This project proposed a new advanced trolley that follows the user to eliminate the need to push the trolley. In addition, the trolley can change its size according to the user's grocery.

INTRODUCTION

The flexi-trolley is an eco-friendly trolley which walks in front of the user by tracking their footsteps. However, depending on your groceries the trolley increases and decreases in size. It will have a specialized spring attached to a sensor on the trolley, whenever there is a lot of groceries the top sensor will manage to maximize the trolley. Whenever the trolley is empty the bottom sensor will minimize the trolley. In addition, the Flexi-trolley is light in terms of weight compared to a normal trolley.

PROBLEM INTRODUCTION

One of the problems that many people face on a daily basis is when visiting a grocery shop. During the COVID-19 pandemic grocery shops have been more crowded and people have been more concerned about sanitizing the trolley handle or wearing gloves before holding the trolley. However, pushing a heavy trolley might cause some back pain for some people, or having to bend down to put the groceries in the trolley.

Concept and Visions

Retailers sell consumer goods or services to customers without caring about the shopper's experience especially in terms of comfort. In addition, the spread of COVID-19 worldwide has

pushed retail shops around the world to a limit that was unpredictable. Overnight there was a noticeable change such as different purchasing behaviors, and a drastic change in the requirements for social distancing. However, the solutions proposed by this project is a new featured trolley, more innovative one which provide a better service by having sensors attached to it that can read the user footsteps in-order to be in front of the user and follows the footsteps wherever it goes. Also, the trolley is flexible in terms of size it can be maximize and minimize according to the user groceries and sustainable in term of the building material where recycled steel will be used, which mean eliminating the excessive weight. Implementing these innovative ideas and features will provide and cover all means of comfort and give the user an easier and healthier grocery shopping experience from a psychological and physical point of view.

GENERATING KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS

After analyzing the survey that was made and distributed for some people. It has been examined that during the Covid-19 pandemic most people sanitize the trolley handle before using it and wear gloves. All people agree that it is difficult to move the trolley while its full of items and hard to check the grocery list. In addition, they agree that it’s hard to carry their personal belong while pushing the trolley. However, 40% of people think that using another trolley is not comfortable after filling the first one and that the grocery can produce an idea to solve the trolley problem. Most people who did this survey where 40 years old and above.

Figure 1

GENERATING IDEAS

Methods that were applied to generate the idea:

- Brainstorming: Discussed between team members what are the problems that people face in the supermarket.
- Empathy Discussion

The problems that people face in the supermarket are:

- Pushing heavy trolleys
- Back pain from bending down to put the groceries in trolley
- Stopping from pushing the trolley every few seconds to check the grocery list
- Worried of getting germs on my hand
- Sanitizing and wearing gloves before holding the trolley handle

Figure 2

EMPATHY DISCUSSION

After conducting several interviews to some people, we have noticed that mostly people are complaining about the trolley while grocery shopping. Some of the main stuff was:

- Afraid of having germs on hand so start sanitizing the trolley handle, wears gloves.

- -Having some back or hand pain from pushing a heavy trolley or bending down to drop of the grocery items in the trolley.
- Stopping every few minutes to check the grocery list which causes crowd.

LIMITATIONS

Strategic risk: There are many new competitors with the same idea, yet our flexi trolley will have a slightly more features than the competitors. The ones that are already invented doesn't have the feature that increases and decreases in size depending on the groceries.

Financial risk: The flexi trolley might not be affordable to individuals since the build fractures require a high-quality slandered s. To overcome this financial risk, the product will have several version gold silver and bronze where the prices and the features varies in order to be affordable for all the users . The invention itself might cost more than 5000 AED for 1 trolley.

System break down : some manufacture errors for activating and deactivating the sensors which means that it might keep on following the previous costumer instead the current one.

COSTUMERS LIST:

We have created possible costumers list that will be interested in our Flexi trolly as they match our criteria of benefiting the most from the features added.

COSTUMERS	CONTACT NUMBER
CARREFOUR MARKET	06-5067734
SHARJAH COOPERATIVE SOCIETY	04-3424444
RAMEZ HYPERMARKET	06-5649870
LULU HYPERMARKET	06-5355345
SPINNEYS	04-3349827
UNION COOPERATIVE	06-5646666
WALMART (DUBAI BRANCH 2022)	-

Table1: costumers list

PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS

- **STANDARD SIZES:**
- **HEIGHT: 95CM**
- **LENGTH: 93.5CM – 143.5CM**
- **WEIGHT: 968 G**

PART NAME	USE FOR	PRICE
RECYCLED STEEL	MAIN BODY	200
ANTI- BACTERIAL HANDLE	FOR SECONDARY AND SAFETY USAGE	350
SPECIALIZED- HEAVY DUTY SPRING	FOR MAXIMIZING AND MINIMIZING FEATURE	750
2X FOOT DETECTOR SENSOR	TO DETECT THE FOOT PRINT	1000
TOTAL	TOTAL PRICE FOR THE PRODUCT	2300AED

Table2: product

MARKETING AND SALES STRATEGY

Price : The company may determine the exact cost of producing and selling an objective, add a markup that may be desirable for profits and price accordingly.

The company will use psychological pricing instead of right numbers pricing to affect customers emotionally.

The company will start targeting individual customers at the early stages with low prices and then target the retail companies with increasing the price in general .

Product : Basic product consists recycled steel as the body+ Anti- bacterial handle+ 2x Foot detector sensor– Specialized- heavy duty spring

Brand name: Flexi-Trolley.

Product package with usage instructions

Maintenance services added depending on the package deal chosen by the cooperation while individuals will have different offers

The product reliability

Place : Direct selling to both individual consumers and to companies. We will have our Flexi-Trolley store for visiting customers as well. It will be located in Dubai.

Promotion: We will increase the budget allocate to promotion. Heavy promotion is needed at the beginning of the project to increase the number of potential customers and to build awareness. Demonstration of the product – free trials samples for one week – large quantity discounts. We will send Ads to individual and business contacts + have sales visits to them.

TEAM

Needed team members	Description	Salary
Entrepreneur – local	Designs the strategy and the general orientation toward the strategic goals. Tracks competition and conduct benchmarking	20000
Legal accountant – accountant – local	Deals with external lawyers and prepares company accounts	15000

Manufacturer and maintainer – nonlocal	Fixing up and maintenance of product parts	8000
Sales and promotion specialist – local	Selling calls and visits – packaging designing advertisements – getting and delivering orders	15000
Purchasing and quality control – nonlocal	Purchasing the best quality specifications with the least possible prices and checks the quality of inventory	6000
Total		64000

Table3: team

FINANCIAL PLAN

	first day	quarter 1	quarter 2	quarter 3	quarter 4		
Cashflows out							
Furniture	5000 packaging and delivery	500 packaging and delivery	500 packaging and delive	500 packaging and delive	500		
4 laptops	8000 parts 2300 X No.	46000 parts	69000 parts	92000 parts	115000		
licence	15000 salary	64000 salary	64000 salary	64000 salary	64000		
visa 2 persons	30000 Pitty cash and vat	800 Pitty cash and vat	800 Pitty cash and vat	800 Pitty cash and vat	800		
Rent - personal	0 sales promotion and ads	30000 sales promotion and ads	10000 sales promotion and	10000 sales promotion and	10000		
	DEWA bills	800 DEWA bills	800 DEWA bills	800 DEWA bills	800		
Total Expenses	58000 Total Expenses	142100 Total Expenses	145100 Total Expenses	168100 Total Expenses	191100 TC	704400	
Cash flows in	60000 20X5000	100000 30X5000	150000 40X5000	200000 50X5000	250000 TR	760000	
Balance	loss 2000	loss -42100	profit 4900	profit 31900	profit 58900 TN	Profit 55600	

Figure 3

INVESTMENT AND USE OF FUNDS

Funds	Use of funds	ROI cash flows in – cash flows out / cash flows out
60000 from Mohamed bin Rashed SME Fund	Startup capital	3.5% - (-29.6% at the end of the first quarter)
Profits of the second quarter - 4900	Reinvest	3.4%
Profits of the third quarter - 31900	Reinvest	19%
Profits of the fourth quarter - 58900	Reinvest	31%
Total investment ROI		8%

TABLE3: INVESTMENT AND USE OF FUNDS

BUSINESS MODEL

A business model canvas was done depending on the 7 areas of business model.

Figure 4

CONCLUSION

To summarize, this report talks about flexi trolley which features have been improved with the help of the methods that have been already taken during the course. From our understanding after applying the methods for our innovation idea. The main steps to understand your project are to generate a survey to your costumers, to generate your idea using different type of methods like brainstorming, gap analysis. To understand what the limitations of your project are. To create a business model and analyze the market, who is your costumer and who is your competitors and how is your idea different from others.

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